

BICOMPONENT PP FIBERS FOR SUSTAINABLE MINERAL BONDED STRAIN HARDENING COMPOSITES

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Motivation

- existing reinforced concrete structures reveal low resistance to impact loading, such as shock, collision, or explosion

impact loading

[1] Kim, K., & Lee, J. (2020). Fragility of bridge columns under vehicle impact using risk analysis. *Advances in Civil Engineering*, 2020, 1-14.

[2] <https://www.nbmcw.com/article-report/infrastructure-construction/transportation-metrorail-airways-waterways/effects-of-blast-loading-on-engineering-structures-an-overview.html>

Research Target

- application of thin layers of strengthening material using innovative, mineral-bonded composites
- economically and ecologically approach

Research Training Group

Mineral-bonded composites for enhanced structural impact safety

<https://www.grk2250.de/>

State of the art

- strain-hardening concrete composites = polymer fibers (2 vol.-%) + concrete matrix
- fiber diameter 10-20 μm , widely used PVA, HDPE, PP

micro-crack bridging for high energy absorption

Approach

Polypropylene fibers (PP):

Melt spinning

Fundamental research on tailored fibers

Approach

- Aim: Improvement of mechanical interlocking combined with high tensile strength
- → Development of bicomponent PP-fibers with increased surface roughness

Shell material: PP + CaCO₃

Core material: pure PP

CaCO₃ particles
average size – 2 μm

- Spinneret
Eleven holes
- Chamber size
Endless fibers
- Online drawing
Enhanced mechanical properties
- Spin finish
Favisan UF 1625: 90% water
+ 10% Tenside composition

Experimental plan

- core/shell ratio 75/25
- incorporating CaCO₃-particle content
- dies size 0.3 x 0.6 mm
- $v = 2400$ m/min
- drawing ratio DR=3

Commercial PP-fiber
(mono), $d = 19.8 \mu\text{m}$

PP + PP,
 $d=27.61 \mu\text{m}$

PP + 10 vol.% CaCO₃,
 $d=28.37 \mu\text{m}$

M1 matrix

GRK2250/I

- basis model mix
- high strength matrix
(Dr. Curosu I. 2016)

FRLC₃ matrix

Optimized model mix

- ↑ sustainability
- LC₃: lower CO₂ emissions,
↑ micro-mechanical
properties

FRLC₃ +SAP matrix

Superabsorbant polymer

- ↑ porosity →
↑ strain-hardening effect

Results – Fiber spinning trials

Analysis of surface morphology and roughness

Commercial PP-fiber (mono),

PP + PP_DR3

PP + 10 vol.% CaCO₃_DR3

Confocal Microscope
(μ Surf expert, Nanofocus AG)

R_a = arithmetic mean
deviation of the surface

Results – Fiber spinning trials

Analysis of mechanical properties

Commercial PP-fiber (mono),

PP + PP_DR3

PP + 10 vol.% CaCO₃_DR3

FAVIMAT+ (Textechno)

- Clamping length (10 mm)
- Velocity (5 mm/min)

Single fiber pull-out test (SFPO)

Sample preparation

computer assisted embedding, $l_e = 1000 \mu\text{m}$

FRLC3 (normal strength r
Beigh B.A.M. et al.

CEM I 52,5 R-SR3/NA (2) (Holc

Limestone (Saxodol 90 LE)

Clay (Liapor)

Gypsum (D) (Fluka (Honeywell))

Quartz sand 0.06–0.2 mm (BCS 41.

H2O

FM MG ACE 460 (BASF)

0,0081

VMA (SIKA)

0,0037

Testing

quasi-static, $v=1,000 \mu\text{m/s}$

dynamic, $v=10,000 \mu\text{m/s}$

Evaluation

$$W_{\text{total}} = W_{\text{chemical bond}} + W_{\text{friction}} + W_{\text{fiber elongation}} + W_{\text{fiber surface deformation}}$$

Results – Quasi-static single fiber pull-out test (Q-SFPO)

– in M1 matrix

– in FRLC3 matrix

– in FRLC3+SAP matrix

Results – Dynamic single fiber pull-out test (D-SFPO)

– in M1 matrix

– in FRLC3 matrix

Results – Surface morphology after Q-SFPO

– in M1 matrix

– in FRLC3 matrix

– in FRLC3+SAP matrix

Results – Surface morphology after D-SFPO

– in M1 matrix

– in FRLC3 matrix

Summary and Outlook

- enhanced energy absorption in FRLC₃ matrix and after SAP addition using rough PP bicomponent fibers compared to 'smooth' monocomponent PP fiber in M1 matrix
- no fiber bridging improvement after SAP addition compared to FRLC₃ regime
- 'smooth' bicomponent PP fibers showed slight bridging improvement in FRLC₃ matrix, even with SAP addition

- composites containing rough PP bicomponent fibers exhibit a propensity for strain-hardening behavior
- SAP utilization enhances the potential for stress transfer through multiple cracking
- rough fibers improve composite properties with less volume fraction

Micro-scale analysis

Macro-scale analysis

BC2.5%

S-BC2.5%

Thank you for your kind attention!

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